

Full Length Article

Effect of copper introduction via wet-impregnation on the performance of Mg-Al mixed metal oxides in selective ammonia oxidation

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Mixed metal oxides
Ammonia oxidation
Copper oxides catalysts
Impregnation
Hydrotalcite-derived materials

ABSTRACT

This study investigates catalytic efficiency of Cu-impregnated Mg-Al hydrotalcite-derived mixed metal oxides as selective ammonia oxidation (NH₃-SCO) catalysts. Copper was introduced via wet impregnation method onto calcined Mg-Al oxides followed by recalcination at 600 and 800 °C. Cu loading was in range 5–15 wt% to determine the loading effect. Obtained materials were characterized by several techniques (X-ray diffraction, low temperature nitrogen physisorption or temperature programmed reduction) and tested as catalysts of NH₃-SCO.

The study revealed that catalytic activity and selectivity are significantly influenced by copper loading and its surface accessibility rather than calcination temperature. Obtained results highlighted crucial role of dispersed, non-isolated, CuO species in selective and efficient NH₃ oxidation. The formation of bulk-like species led to unselective oxidation and formation of side products, while presence of isolated CuO species lowers the activity. The characterisation results together with catalytic tests show that enhancing copper accessibility and reducibility on the materials surface result in better catalytic efficiency.

The materials impregnation allows greater surface exposure of active copper species compared to materials where Cu was introduced during parent hydrotalcite co-precipitation. Results suggest that use of well-developed surface area support allow copper loading increase without formation of undesired bulk-like species.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) is colorless, corrosive and toxic gas with distinct, pungent odor. It is one of the air pollutants closely monitored by the European Environmental Agency (EEA), as reducing NH₃ emissions remains a significant challenge for long-term air quality management strategies [1]. Exposure to ammonia poses serious health risks, including irritation of the skin, eyes and respiratory tract, and at high concentrations (~10000 ppm), it can even be fatal [2]. Beyond human health, ammonia contributes to environmental degradation by forming atmospheric aerosols that promotes soil and surface water acidification [3]. This leads to eutrophication, where water become enriched with nitrogen and phosphorus, often originating from nitrogen-based fertilizers

[4].

Annual ammonia emissions are estimated at ~5600 kt [5], with agriculture accounting for around 95 % of the total emission [1,4]. Major agricultural sources include nitrogen fertilizers, livestock waste and biomass combustion. Non-agriculture sources include ammonia releases from industrial activities such as urea production, chemical and pharmaceutical processes, and combustion processes in energy and transport sectors [1]. In industry, NH₃ emissions are particularly associated with selective catalytic reduction (SCR NO_x) and selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR NO_x) technologies for nitrogen oxides (NO_x) abatement. Here, NH₃ or urea is used as a reducing agent (NH₃/NO > 1.2). However, unreacted ammonia often escapes in the exhaust gases – a phenomenon known as ‘ammonia slip’ – resulting in secondary

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2026.165973>

Received 4 September 2025; Received in revised form 9 January 2026; Accepted 16 January 2026

Available online 17 January 2026

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pollution [6].

With ongoing industrialization and globalization, ammonia-related air pollution is expected to increase. Thus, effective mitigation strategies are urgently needed. Among available techniques, such as bio-filtration [7], adsorption [8] and thermal oxidation [8], selective catalytic oxidation of ammonia (NH₃-SCO) has emerged as one of the most promising solutions [3,9,10]. The alternative methods have drawbacks that are limiting their potential implementation: bio-filtration, is limited by the operational parameters such as temperature, humidity, light and pH [7]; adsorption is ineffective in humid environment due to competitive adsorption between NH₃ and H₂O [8]; and thermal oxidation requires the high operation temperatures (1200–1300 °C) [11].

In contrast, NH₃-SCO enables the conversion of ammonia into nitrogen (N₂) and water vapour (H₂O) (Eq. (1)) over a wide NH₃ concentrations range and in the presence of typical exhaust gas components (CO_x, NO_x, H₂O, or SO_x). When properly optimized, the process can operate below 400 °C [12,13]. However, a key challenge is to suppress the formation of undesirable by-product, such as nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) which can form through competing oxidation pathways (Eqs. (2)–(4)) [13].

Catalysts based on noble metals (e.g. Pt, Ru [14–16]) can achieve total NH₃ conversion at relatively low temperatures (150–300 °C), but typically favor the formation of undesired NO_x over N₂ production [3,10]. In contrast, transition metal oxides (e.g. Fe-based, Ce-V compounds and Cu-based catalysts such as CuO oxides or mixed oxides systems like CuO-CeO₂ [17]) offer better selectivity toward N₂, but usually require temperatures in range 300–450 °C [3,10,18]. The simultaneous achievement of high N₂ selectivity (90–100 %) and complete NH₃ conversion at relatively low temperatures (150–250 °C) is fulfilled by hybrid catalysts combining noble-metal sites with copper oxide systems (e.g. Pt/CuO/Al₂O₃ [19], RuO₂-CuO/Al-ZrO₂ [20]). These catalysts effectively couple the low-temperature activity characteristic for noble metals with the N₂-selectivity typical for copper-oxide systems.

Copper-based catalysts have emerged as particularly attractive due to their moderate cost, redox activity and favourable balance between the activity and selectivity. However, performance depends strongly on the oxidation state, dispersion and surface accessibility of Cu-species. Our previous research demonstrated that Cu-containing mixed metal oxides, prepared via co-precipitation and calcination of parent precursor materials, exhibited promising activity below 350 °C, achieving NH₃ conversion levels 80–100 % and N₂ selectivity between 60–80 % [9,21,22]. These results were attributed to the fine dispersion and surface accessibility of CuO species. However, it must be noted that currently NH₃-SCO process is commercially used only in automotive industry, and its utilization in stationary sources has not been applied yet.

Four possible reaction pathways have been reported for NH₃-SCO, including the imide, hydrazine, internal selective catalytic reduction (*i*-SCR), and N₂-mechanisms [10]. Among these, the existing literature identifies the *i*-SCR pathway as the dominant mechanism over copper-based catalysts [10,23–28]. In this mechanism, ammonia is partially oxidized to NO_x, which is then reduced by residual NH₃ at active sites on Cu to form N₂ and H₂O. The initial oxidation of NH₃ is usually the rate-limiting step and proceeds via a redox cycle between Cu²⁺ and Cu⁺. Surface oxygen species are mainly involved at lower temperatures, while lattice oxygen contributes at higher temperatures. The overall N₂ selectivity depends on maintaining the correct balance between NH₃

oxidation and NO_x reduction, with excessive oxidation promoting the undesirable formation of NO or N₂O [10,27].

In the present study, we focus on enhancing both the copper surface area and its dispersion through the use of wet impregnation instead of co-precipitation. One of the major advantages of impregnation is its simplicity and possibility of controlled deposition of a desired metal amount or active component onto the surface of the support. The technique allows to deposit the active phase uniformly onto the support surface and into accessible pores. High dispersion of active metals Co, Cu, Cr, and Mo deposited by wet impregnation on CeO₂-MgO supports was confirmed by TEM [29] or by H₂-TPR analysis for copper oxide deposited on zirconia support [30]. However, impregnation can also bring disadvantages such as limitation by the available surface area of the support, possible pore blockage leading to reduced accessibility, formation of an inhomogeneous or uneven active layer, and potential interactions between the impregnated species and the support [31,32]. Interaction between the impregnated species and the support was reported by Jablonska et al. [33] who prepared a Cu/Al₂O₃ catalyst via impregnation of γ-Al₂O₃ with copper nitrate and XRD analysis revealed formation not only CuO but also CuAl₂O₄ phases, indicating a strong interaction between the deposited copper species and the alumina support.

Mg–Al mixed metal oxides were selected as carriers because they represent one of the most extensively studied and well-defined families of mixed metal oxides [34]. Owing to the tunable Mg/Al molar ratio, these materials offer control over chemical composition and surface properties [35]. Upon calcination, hydrotalcite precursors form homogeneous MgO–Al₂O₃ mixed oxides [36] with high specific surface area [35,37], good thermal stability [34] and balanced acid–base properties [38,39]. Calcined Mg–Al hydrotalcite-derived mixed oxides have been shown to play an active role in NH₃-SCO catalysis beyond that of an inert carrier, particularly through their influence on copper speciation, ammonia adsorption, and reaction selectivity. In NH₃-SCO, the Mg–Al carrier was shown to influence the acid–base properties of the catalyst surface, thereby affecting ammonia adsorption strength and reaction pathways [40]. The results suggest that tuning the Mg/Al ratio, which modifies the acid–base properties of Mg–Al mixed oxides, affects NH₃ adsorption and consequently N₂ selectivity [40]. This behavior was consistently observed when Cu catalysts supported on Mg–Al mixed oxides were compared with those supported on more acidic single oxides, confirming that the carrier actively determines NH₃-SCO selectivity [25]. In studies focused on Cu-Mg–Al hydrotalcite-derived catalysts for ammonia oxidation, surface basicity and homogeneous copper dispersion were identified as important factors governing N₂ selectivity [21,40]. In addition, LDH-derived Mg–Al supports were reported to enhance copper dispersion and thermal stability, which directly correlates with improved catalytic performance in NH₃ oxidation [41].

Therefore, our goal is to introduce the Cu-species by impregnation onto Mg–Al mixed metal oxides derived from hydrotalcite-like precursors. We hypothesized that this approach can improve CuO reducibility and surface availability, thus enhancing catalytic efficiency. To validate this, we compare the structural, surface and catalytic properties of impregnated Cu/MgAl systems with those prepared by co-precipitation [21], aiming to identify the relationship between CuO form (dispersed vs. bulk-like) and NH₃-SCO efficiency. Our findings can provide new insights into tailoring CuO-based catalysts for selective ammonia oxidation and optimizing them for potential applications in flue gas treatment.

2. Methodology

2.1. Preparation of mixed metal oxide catalysts

2.1.1. Synthesis of hydrotalcite-derived precursor

The hydrotalcite-like material Mg_{0.67}Al_{0.33}(OH)₂(CO₃)_{0.165}·*n*H₂O

was synthesized using a co-precipitation method. As the source of cations, the aqueous solution of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Penta) and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Penta) of total cation concentration $c = 1 \text{ mol/dm}^3$ was used. The precipitation was carried out using a solution containing NaOH (3 mol/dm^3 , Penta) and Na_2CO_3 (0.5 mol/dm^3 , Penta). The synthesis involved the simultaneous dropwise addition of the metal nitrate and the precipitation solution into the heated reactor containing distilled water ($\sim 200 \text{ ml}$). The synthesis was performed till the full consumption of cation solution. The formed slurry was stirred vigorously during synthesis and aging (1 h). The pH 10 inside the reactor was controlled during synthesis by addition of precipitation agent. The synthesis temperature was set at 65°C . After aging, materials were filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 60°C .

2.1.2. Preparation of mixed metal oxides

The Mg-Al mixed metal oxides were obtained by the calcination of hydroxalcalite-like precursor at two different temperatures: 600°C and 800°C for 6 h in flow of air. After calcination, the samples were grinded to powder.

Each calcined MgAlO material was divided into four portions. The three portions of each group were wet-impregnated by $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Penta) to achieve materials with copper loadings of 5 %, 10 % and 15 % by weight. The fourth portion left unimpregnated and served as the reference material.

First of all, the water uptake of the unimpregnated catalysts was determined by gradually adding distilled water to 0.5 g of 600-MgAl or 800-MgAl catalyst until they became moist but without excess liquid. This step was done two times for each catalyst and the average absorption was calculated (4.277 ml/g for 600-MgAl and 3.982 ml/g for 800-MgAl). Based on these results the amount of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Penta) was calculated to achieve copper loadings of 5 %, 10 % and 15 % by weight. The impregnation solutions were prepared by dissolving the required amount ($0.475\text{--}1.711 \text{ g}$, depending on required wt.%) of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the desired volume of distilled water ($9.3\text{--}10.9 \text{ ml}$). Depending on the required catalyst amount after impregnation ($2.5\text{--}3 \text{ g}$), approximately 2.4 g of unimpregnated catalysts were weighed and mixed with the impregnation solutions. The mixture was left to stand for 15 min, then it was manually stirred and subsequently allowed to rest for 1 h.

After the impregnation, the samples were dried at 60°C for 24 h in an oven and subsequently recalcined under the same conditions as initial calcination (600°C and 800°C), resulting in mixed oxides of Mg, Al and Cu.

The final materials were labeled as follows: 600-MgAl and 800-MgAl for the unimpregnated samples, 600-IMP-CuX and 800-IMP-CuX (where X represents 5, 10 or 15 wt%) for the impregnated samples.

2.2. Materials characterization

Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) was performed on a CONTR AA 700 spectrometer, AnalyticJena. Before measurements, samples were mineralized with use of HCl. Concentration of Cu, Mg and Al were established based on characteristic lines: 324.8, 285.2 and 309.3 nm , respectively.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed with use of Vega 4, Tescan. Images were collected with the accelerating voltage 30 keV using the backscattered electrons (BSE) and secondary electrons (SE) modes. Before analysis, samples were gold sputtered.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements were performed with the use of the high-resolution electron microscope Titan G2 60–300 kV (FEI Company). The microscope was equipped with a field-emission gun (FEG), a monochromator, three condenser lens systems, an objective lens system, an image correction (Cs-corrector), an HAADF detector, and an EDS (Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy) spectrometer with a Si(Li) detector. Microscopic studies of the catalysts were carried out at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV .

The catalyst samples were ground into a fine powder using an agate mortar. The resulting powder of catalyst was suspended in 99.8 % ethanol (POCH) to form a suspension, which was subsequently inserted into an ultrasonic homogenizer for 10 s. The suspension of the catalysts was applied to a 200-mesh nickel grid covered with Formvar and stabilized with carbon (Ted Pella Company). The grid was then left on filter paper for ethanol evaporation. The copper grids with deposited samples were inserted into a single-tilt holder and transferred to the electron microscope.

The element mapping in the catalyst samples was carried out in STEM mode by collecting step-by-step EDS spectra of each corresponding pixel in the map. The collected maps were presented as a coloured matrix of pixels, where the intensity corresponded to the amount of the element in the mapping place of the sample.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was done on a Rigaku Smart Lab diffractometer with use of the $\text{Co K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.179 \text{ nm}$) in the range of $5\text{--}90^\circ$. Crystallite size was calculated using Debye-Scherrer equation: $L = (k\lambda)/(\beta\cos\theta)$ (k – shape factor (0.89), λ – X-ray wavelength, β – line broadening at half of the maximum intensity (FWHM), θ – Bragg angle).

Low-temperature nitrogen adsorption was performed in a 3Flex Micromeritics sorptometer at temperature -196°C . Before measurements, samples were outgassed under vacuum at 350°C for approx. 24 h. Specific surface area was calculated based on the Brunauer–Emmet–Teller (BET) method, while pore volume was established by the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method.

Temperature programmed reduction with use of hydrogen (H_2 -TPR) was performed in an AutoChem II 2920 Micromeritics apparatus with a thermal conductivity detection (TCD). The results were collected at following conditions: temperature range $40\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$ with heating rate 10°C/min in the flow of 10 mol.% H_2/Ar (30 ml/min). Before an experiment, samples (0.03 g) were outgassed in the flow of Ar (50 ml/min) at 500°C for 1 h.

UV-VIS diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded with use of a Shimadzu UV-260, IRS-2600Plus spectrophotometer in the range of $200\text{--}800 \text{ nm}$. The direct optical band gaps were estimated based on Tauc's plot.

TPO-TPR-TPO measurements were performed with use of AutoChem II 2920, Micromeritics. The procedure involved:

- (i) outgassing: samples were outgassed at 300°C for 30 min in the flow of He (50 ml/min);
- (ii) first temperature programmed oxidation cycle (TPO-I): conducted in the range $50\text{--}600^\circ\text{C}$ or $50\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$ (depending the calcination temperature) under an oxidizing atmosphere (10 mol. % O_2/He , 50 ml/min) with the heating rate 20°C/min , followed by a 30-minute isothermal step at the maximum temperature;
- (iii) TPR cycle: after cooling to 50°C , the reduction was performed under H_2 -containing atmosphere (10 mol. % H_2/Ar , 50 ml/min) using the same heating range and rate as for TPO-I;
- (iv) The second TPO cycle (TPO-II): conducted under the same conditions as TPO-I.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed in a Prevac system equipped with a hemispherical analyser (VG SCIENTA R3000) and a monochromatised Al $\text{K}\alpha$ source ($E = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$). The surface charge was compensated by a low energy electron flood gun (FS40A-PS). For analysis, the core-level spectra of Cu 2p, Al 2p, Mg 2p, O 1s and C 1s were collected and calibrated to the position of XPS C 1s peak at 285.0 eV attributed to adventitious carbon. The fitting procedure was done in the Casa XPS software.

Reactive frontal chromatography with use of N_2O (N_2O -RFC) was measured using AutoChem II 290, Micromeritics online connected with a quadrupole mass spectrometer (HPR-20EGA, Hiden Analytical) monitoring signals for $m/z = 30$ and 44 (N_2O), $m/z = 28$ (N_2), $m/z = 32$ (O_2), and $m/z = 16$ (NH_3). The measurements were divided into two

steps: (i) sample reduction in the range of 40–350 °C, in a flow of 10 mol. % H₂/Ar (30 ml/min) with an isothermal step at 350 °C (1 h); (ii) N₂O chemisorption over the pre-reduced sample in a flow of 3 mol. % N₂O/He (30 ml/min) at 90 °C. The results of low-temperature reduction were recorded using a TCD detector. The procedure of the copper surface area calculation was described previously by Jensen et al. [42].

Temperature programmed desorption of ammonia (NH₃-TPD) was measured with use of AutoChem II 290, Micromeritics. Prior to an analysis, samples (0.1 g) were outgassed in a flow of He (50 ml/min) for 30 min at temperature 550 °C or 750 °C (regarding calcination temperature). After cleaning, the samples were cooled to 75 °C and saturated in a flow of 5 mol. % NH₃/He (50 ml/min for 1 h). After full surface saturation with ammonia, the weakly adsorbed molecules were removed by a flow of He (50 ml/min for 100 min) at temperature 75 °C. After that the programmed desorption starts. The NH₃ was desorbed under the flow of He (50 ml/min) in the temperature range 75–600 °C (heating rate 20 °C/min), with an isothermal period at 600 °C (20 min).

2.3. Catalytic tests

Selective catalytic oxidation of ammonia was studied in a flow quartz reactor with inner diameter of 4 mm at the atmospheric pressure. Measurements were taken in the temperature range 250–350 °C with isothermal steps every 25 °C (180 min) and temperature rate 1 °C/min between steps. The inlet reaction gas mixture was composed of 350 ppm of NH₃ and synthetic air as balance, with total flow rate of 100 ml/min. The stability tests were performed at 325 °C for 70 h with the same reaction gas mixture. The catalytic measurements were carried out in a Carlo Erba chromatographic furnace, which ensures a constant temperature throughout the reactor volume. The reaction temperature was additionally monitored by an auxiliary thermocouple placed close to the catalyst bed, and the temperature variation did not exceed ±1 °C. Before experiments, samples (0.2 g of grain size ~0.160–0.350 mm) were activated in an air flow (100 ml/min) at 200 °C (60 min) to heat the catalytic bed up to the reaction starting temperature and avoid possible sorption of ammonia at lower temperatures.

Ammonia, water vapor and the reaction products, i.e. nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), were detected by a FT-IR detector (Antaris IGS, Nicolet).

The *ammonia conversion* (Eq. (5)) and *nitrogen selectivity* (Eq. (6)) were calculated as follows:

$$(NH_3)_{conv} = \left(\frac{[NH_3]_{in} - [NH_3]_{out}}{[NH_3]_{in}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

where [NH₃]_{in} is inlet ammonia concentration, [NH₃]_{out} is outlet ammonia concentration at steady state.

$$(N_2)_{sel} = \left(1 - \frac{[NO]_{out} + [NO_2]_{out} + 2[N_2O]_{out}}{[NH_3]_{in} - [NH_3]_{out}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where: (N₂)_{sel} is selectivity to dinitrogen, [NO]_{out}, [NO₂]_{out} and [N₂O]_{out} are outlet steady state concentrations of NO, NO₂ and N₂O, respectively.

The *selectivity to side products* was calculated using equation (Eq. (7)).

$$S_i = \frac{[i]_{out}^*}{\sum [i]_{out}^*} \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

where: S_i is selectivity to the side-product i; *related to the molar amount of reacted NH₃

The *yield of products* was calculated as follow (Eq. (8))

$$y_i = \frac{y_a}{y_t} \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

where y_a is actual yield of product, y_t is theoretical yield of product i.

The actual yield of product i is its concentration read for specific temperature. Since the concentration of nitrogen cannot be established

in the direct way, the yield of N₂ was calculated as follow (Eq. (9)):

$$y_{N_2} = \frac{[NH_3]_{in} - [NH_3]_{out} - [NO]_{out} - [NO_2]_{out} - 2[N_2O]_{out}}{[NH_3]_{in}} \cdot 100 \quad (9)$$

The theoretical yield of products was calculated based on the possible NH₃-SCO reactions, assuming that 100 % of ammonia gives only one nitrogen-based product. Therefore: [NO] = [NH₃], [NO₂] = [NH₃], [N₂O] = $\frac{1}{2}$ [NH₃].

3. Results

3.1. Catalysts characterization

3.1.1. Chemical composition

Chemical composition of the prepared catalysts is summarized in Table 1. The calculated Cu/(Mg + Al) weight ratios, determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), align well with the intended (theoretical) values, confirming the efficient control over copper loading during the impregnation process. As expected, the Cu content increases progressively with nominal loading (5, 10 and 15 wt%).

Slight differences between the measured and intended values may be attributed to two factors. First, the thermal decomposition of precursor species (i.e. carbonates and nitrates) during high-temperature calcination lead to the release of CO₂ and NO_x gases [40,43], resulting in changes to the overall elemental composition. Second, the presence of non-stoichiometric oxides with varying oxygen contents may affect the calculation of metal weight percentages. Despite these deviations, the compositional data remain consistent with the intended values.

3.1.2. Morphology and textural properties

The XRD patterns of the 600-IMP and 800-IMP series (Fig. 1A) confirm the presence of three crystalline phases: tenorite (CuO), periclase (MgO) and spinel-like phase attributed to MgAl₂O₄. The corresponding diffraction peaks are assigned as follow: CuO at 2θ~41, 57, 69, 78 and 82° (ICDD PDF-2 card No. 00-041-0254); MgO at 2θ~51 and 74° (ICDD PDF-2 card No. 01-071-9574) and spinel at 2θ~36, 43, 45, 57, 66, 70 and 77° (ICDD PDF-2 card No. 01-075-4041).

In the reference materials (600-MgAl and 800-MgAl), only MgO and spinel-type phases are observed, confirming the decomposition of the hydrotalcite precursor into mixed oxides. The calculated crystalline sizes for these phases are 3.2 nm (MgO) and 2.6 nm (spinel) in 600-MgAl, and 3.6 nm (MgO) and 3.7 nm (spinel) in 800-MgAl (Table 2). The calculations suggest that increasing calcination temperature from 600 °C to 800 °C does not significantly affect the crystallite size.

Upon copper impregnation and subsequent re-calcination at 600 °C, the periclase crystallite size remains nearly unchanged, while the spinel crystallites grow progressively with increasing Cu content. A similar trend is observed in the 800-IMP series: both the periclase and spinel crystallites undergo notable crystallite growth (Table 2). This crystallite growth is consistent with the appearance of sharper, more intense XRD reflections for MgO and spinel in the 800-IMP samples, indicating enhanced crystallinity compared to 800-MgAl reference (Fig. 1A).

The introduction of copper introduces an additional crystalline phase – tenorite (CuO) (Fig. 1A). However, the detectability strongly depends on copper loading and calcination temperature. The pronounced diffraction peaks corresponding to CuO are observed only for 600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15, with calculated crystallite size of 9.2 and 28.0 nm, respectively (Table 2). In the samples with lower Cu loadings, CuO peaks are either weak or obscured by overlapping reflections from the MgO or spinel phases.

Although the sample composition suggests the possible formation of Al₂O₃ phase (expected 2θ~30, 41 (rel. intensity = 100 %), 44, 51, 62, 68, 79 and 81°; ICDD PDF-2 card No. 01-076-8186), no distinct peaks of Al₂O₃ were detected. This may be due to: (i) Al is preferentially incorporated into spinel-like framework, (ii) the formation of amorphous or

Table 1
Chemical composition of catalysts.

Series	Sample code	Intended composition ^[a]					Measured composition wt. % ^[b]				
		wt. %	wt. %	wt. %	mol. % ratio	wt.% ratio	wt. %	wt. %	wt. %	mol. % ratio	wt.% ratio
		Cu	Mg	Al	Mg/Al	Cu/(Mg+Al)	Cu	Mg	Al	Mg/Al	Cu/(Mg + Al)
600-IMP	600-MgAl	–	35.4	19.6	67:33	–	–	33.6	20.2	1.9	–
	600-IMP-Cu5	5.0	33.2	18.2	67:33	0.1	4.7	26.5	16.6	1.8	0.1
	600-IMP-Cu10	10.0	31.0	17.2	67:33	0.2	9.8	21.4	14.7	1.6	0.3
	600-IMP-Cu15	15.0	28.8	15.9	67:33	0.3	14.4	23.7	14.8	1.8	0.4
800-IMP	800-MgAl	–	35.4	19.6	67:33	–	–	30.3	18.7	1.8	–
	800-IMP-Cu5	5.0	33.2	18.2	67:33	0.1	5.1	28.7	17.5	1.8	0.1
	800-IMP-Cu10	10.0	31.0	17.2	67:33	0.2	11.2	28.2	17.8	1.8	0.2
	800-IMP-Cu15	15.0	28.8	15.9	67:33	0.3	15.7	26.9	15.5	1.9	0.4

[a] Calculated based on the theoretical Cu (wt. %) and Mg, Al (mol. %) loading; assuming that the oxygen number is 45 wt% due to formation of CuO, MgO, Al₂O₃ and MgAl₂O₄.

[b] Determined by AAS.

nanocrystalline Al₂O₃ below the detection limit, or (iii) peak overlap with signals from spinel [21].

Low-temperature adsorption of nitrogen analysis was performed to evaluate the textural properties of the reference and Cu-impregnated Mg-Al oxide materials (Fig. 1B, Fig. 1C, and Table 2). The resulting adsorption-desorption N₂ isotherms (Fig. 1B) for all samples exhibit features characteristic of type IV isotherms [44], confirming the presence of mesoporous structures. The hysteresis loops are indicative of capillary condensation in mesopores and differ between the sample series. The reference materials (600-MgAl and 800-MgAl) show H3-type hysteresis, typically assigned with the slit like or plate like pores formed by aggregates of lamellar particles [45]. In contrast, the Cu-impregnated samples show H2-type hysteresis loops, which are commonly linked to pore systems with narrow necks and wide bodies – so called ‘ink-bottle’ pores [45] – suggesting change in pore geometry due to copper addition and re-calcination.

Pore size distribution analysis (Fig. 1C) supports these findings. All samples exhibit mesopore maxima within the 10–40 nm range. However, a distinct shift towards wider average pore diameters is observed with the increasing copper content and calcination temperature. The 600-IMP-Cu10 sample shows a secondary maximum in the 90–100 nm range.

The calculated BET surface areas (Table 2) reveal a clear trend: both copper loading and calcination temperature significantly reduce the specific surface area (S_{BET}) of the materials. The reference 600-MgAl sample exhibits a high S_{BET} of 204 m²/g, which decreases progressively with increasing Cu wt.% loading, reaching 143 m²/g for 600-IMP-Cu15. Similarly, the S_{BET} of the IMP-800 series drops from 157 m²/g (800-MgAl) to 60 m²/g for 800-IMP-Cu15. This decline in S_{BET} can be attributed to: (i) increase of MgO and spinel crystallite size after the re-calcination step, and (ii) formation and surface coverage by CuO particles, which typically exhibit much lower S_{BET} (20–50 m²/g), and could clog the pore inlet for N₂ molecules used for physisorption measurement [46,47].

SEM micrographs of the sample series 600-IMP and 800-IMP are shown in Fig. 1D; while higher-resolution images are provided in Supplementary, Fig. S1–S8.

The SEM micrographs of the reference materials, 600-MgAl and 800-MgAl (Fig. 1D, Fig. S1 and Fig. S5), demonstrate distinct morphological features as a function of calcination temperature. The 600-MgAl sample exhibits irregular, fluffy clusters with plate-like domains (marked yellow in Fig. S1) interspersed with semi-crystalline or amorphous cloud-like regions (marked blue in Fig. S1). In contrast, 800-MgAl exposes more well-defined plate-like microstructures with sharpened edges (marked yellow in Fig. S5), indicating a higher degree of crystallinity induced by the elevated calcination temperature.

Copper impregnation leads to morphological changes, with features evolving progressively with increasing Cu loading. In the 600-IMP-Cu5

sample, low copper loading results in formation of small comb-like structures (marked yellow in Fig. S2), that remains the fluffy plate-like. These features are accompanied by the semi-crystalline phases (marked blue). In the 800-IMP-Cu5 sample, the fluffy areas transform into the more defined crystalline structure and forms a comb-like structure on the samples’ surface (marked yellow in Fig. S6).

Further increasing the copper loading to 10 wt% and 15 wt% in the 600-IMP series (600-IMP-Cu10 and 600-IMP-Cu15) enhances the visibility and definition of comb-like surface features (marked yellow in Fig. S3 and Fig. S4). While some amorphous features persist, regions of enhanced crystallinity become more apparent (marked blue, Fig. S4), suggesting improved ordering induced by the higher Cu concentration and thermal treatment. Similarly, in the 800-IMP series, higher Cu loadings (800-IMP-Cu10 and 800-IMP-Cu15) lead to the formation of distinctive flower-like assemblies, composed of numerous leaf-like separate combs (Fig. S7 and Fig. S8). These microstructures are distributed across the entire surface and become increasingly prominent and larger with higher copper loading.

The EDS maps of materials (Fig. 2 and Fig. S9) show homogeneous distribution of Mg and Al across all samples, with no apparent signs of elements segregation or aggregation. The dark or ‘empty’ regions observed in the EDS maps of Mg and Al are attributed to topographic features – including surface depressions, edge effects and/or electron interactions with sample rather than the compositional voids.

The 600-IMP-Cu5 sample (Fig. S9(a)), exhibits a non-uniform distribution of Cu, characterized by areas of high Cu concentration interspersed with Cu-deficient regions dominated by Mg and Al. As the copper content increases, the Cu distribution becomes progressively more uniform, as seen in 600-IMP-Cu10 and 600-IMP-Cu15 (Fig. S9(c) and Fig. S9(a)). For the latter, the Cu map aligns closely with those of Mg and Al, indicating effective dispersion of the impregnated phase following re-calcination.

A similar trend is observed for the 800-IMP series. At 5 wt% and 10 wt% loadings, 800-IMP-Cu5 (Fig. S9(b)) and 800-IMP-Cu10 (Fig. S9(d)), Cu is evenly dispersed, with no evidence of significant clustering or surface enrichment. However, in the 800-IMP-Cu15 sample (Fig. 2(b)), distinct Cu-enrichment regions (highlighted with white circles) become evident. These regions are clearly defined in the Cu map, but do not correspond to any depletion in the Mg or Al maps, suggesting that implementation of Cu does not result in replacement for Mg and Al in oxides framework.

The TEM investigation was performed for selected samples 800-IMP-Cu5, 800-IMP-Cu15, and 600-IMP-Cu15, and the corresponding HRTEM and STEM-EDS results are shown in Figs. 3–5. The obtained images confirm the presence of the same crystalline phases as identified by XRD, namely MgAl₂O₄, MgO, and CuO. The dispersion of CuO particles varies among the samples: in 800-IMP-Cu15, the CuO particles are significantly larger compared to those in 800-IMP-Cu5, which is consistent with the

Fig. 1. A. Phase composition: P - MgO, S - MgAl₂O₄, T - CuO (B) Textural properties. Ads - adsorption curve, Des - desorption curve (C) Pore distribution (D) SEM micrographs (SE+BSE mode) (a) calcined at 600 °C and (b) calcined at 800 °C. Images in higher resolution are presented in supplementary to this article.

XRD findings. The 600-IMP-Cu15 sample exhibits a similar CuO particle size to that observed for 800-IMP-Cu5.

Given that the copper-containing phase is the least abundant in these materials, the intensity of its diffraction features is much lower compared to those of MgO and MgAl₂O₄. As a result, the FFT patterns mainly display the most intense CuO ($-1\ 1\ 1$) lattice plane, while other, less intense CuO reflections are suppressed by the strong diffraction from the dominant phases. Moreover, the CuO phase in the samples may be highly dispersed even at the atomic level, which prevents its detection with much higher intensity of the dominant phases and large number of lattice fringes visible in the HRTEM images. Therefore, it cannot be unambiguously concluded whether Cu species are also present in another phase, such as a Cu-spinel-like structure or strongly interacting Cu species anchored to the support. However, this possibility cannot be excluded, since the limited visibility of Cu-related lattice fringes and

their partial overlap with the spinel and MgO phases could mask such interactions.

3.1.3. Reducibility and red-ox properties

The H₂-TPR reduction profiles, Fig. 6A and Fig. 6B, show the reduction behavior of the samples within the temperature range of 40–800 °C. The reduction signals reveal the presence of multiple Cu species differing in dispersion and interaction with the support. Additional deconvoluted profiles are presented in Supplementary, Fig. S10.

For the 600-IMP samples, the first H₂ consumption peak (a) is observed at 200–230 °C and is attributed to the reduction of dispersed CuO species [21]. For the 800-IMP samples, this peak is shifted to slightly lower temperatures (185–195 °C), indicating slightly enhanced reducibility. Deconvolution of the (a) peak (Fig. S10) reveals two partially overlapping sub-peaks (a₁) and (a₂), likely associated with

Table 2
Crystallite size of oxide phases, textural properties and H₂-TPR results.

Sample code	L ^[a] (nm)			S _{BET} ^[b] (m ² /g)	M _{H₂} ^[c] (mmol/g) 40–400 °C	M _{H₂} ^[d] (%) 40–400 °C	T _{H₂} ^[e] (mmol/g)
	T	P	S				
600-MgAl	–	3.2	2.6	204	–	–	–
600-IMP-Cu5	3.5	3.8	5.2	192	0.480	48	0.741
600-IMP-Cu10	3.1	3.8	5.2	155	0.954	62	1.544
600-IMP-Cu15	9.2	3.9	6.2	143	1.422	68	2.269
800-MgAl	–	3.7	3.7	157	–	–	–
800-IMP-Cu5	–	7.6	9.3	112	0.399	45	0.804
800-IMP-Cu10	2.9	5.7	11.0	88	0.760	54	1.765
800-IMP-Cu15	28.0	13.8	13.4	60	1.246	57	2.474

[a] Crystallite size (*L*) calculated based on XRD diffraction lines: CuO (T), position 41° (*d* = 2.523, intensity 100 %); MgAl₂O₄ (S), position 43° (*d* = 2.437, intensity 100 %); MgO (P), position 50° (*d* = 2.106, intensity 100 %);

[b] Specific surface area calculated by BET method;

[c] Measured H₂ consumption from H₂-TPR in temperature range 40–4000 °C;

[d] Percentage of H₂ consumption up to 400 °C related to total measured H₂ consumption;

[e] Theoretical H₂ consumption assuming that only Cu²⁺ is reduced; based on AAS results.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs (SE+BSE mode) of (A) 600-IMP-Cu15 and (B) 800-IMP-Cu15 and the EDS maps of Cu, Mg and Al distribution.

dispersed CuO nanoparticles of different sizes [48].

A second major reduction peak (c) is observed in range of 560–640 °C for 600-IMP and up to 800 °C for the 800-IMP series. This peak can be attributed to the reduction of hardly reducible Cu containing species like Cu²⁺ species in interaction with Mg-Al spinel [21] or thermally stable isolated Cu²⁺ species [49–51].

The H₂-TPR profile of 800-IMP-Cu15 shows the presence of additional maximum (b) at 230 °C that may be ascribed to the reduction of CuO bulk-like species [21]. Despite that this maximum is clearly visible only for 800-IMP-Cu15, the deconvolution (Fig. S10) suggests that similar features are present in the profiles of all the Cu-containing materials. Comparison of the peak area related to maximum (b) shows increase of peak area (b) (Fig. S10) with the increase of Cu content.

The formation of different Cu species as a function of loading and temperature is consistent with findings by Luo et al [48]. At low Cu loadings, copper form primarily finely dispersed CuO and Cu interacts with the Mg-Al spinel. In contrast, the bulk-like CuO species, require higher Cu loadings [48]. A similar trend is observed in the present study.

Quantitative H₂ consumption data, summarized in Table 2, shows that the total H₂ consumption (T_{H₂}) increases with Cu loading, reflecting the growing Cu content. Simultaneously, the proportion of H₂ consumed below 400 °C (M_{H₂-400}) also rises, indicating that higher copper content leads to a greater fraction of easily reducible CuO species. This trend holds regardless of calcination temperature.

The UV-vis-DRS absorption spectra of the 600-IMP and 800-IMP samples (Fig. 6C) reveal three distinct absorption regions corresponding to different types of CuO particles. The first region (I), observed in

the range of 200–300 nm range, is ascribed to the O²⁻ → Cu²⁺ charge transfer transition in CuO and Cu-containing spinel-type structures [52–54]. A second absorption region (II), appearing between 320–360 nm, is associated to the O²⁻ → Cu²⁺ charge transfer transitions in bulk-like/oligomeric CuO and/or Cu-spinels [53,55]. The third region (III), observed between 600–900 nm, is attributed to d-d transitions of Cu²⁺ (²E_g → ²T_{2g}) in distorted CuO bulk-like species [53,54]. The reference MgAl supports (600-MgAl and 800-MgAl) exhibit no significant absorption bands across the measured range.

The Cu-impregnated samples show a progressive increase in absorption intensity with increasing Cu loading, what is consistent with the H₂-TPR results (Fig. 6A-B). The intensity of the low-wavelength bands (<250 nm) correlates with the presence of highly dispersed Cu species, while the features in the 260–300 nm range are attributed to the formation of spinel-like phases. At the same time, well-defined absorption features within region II (320–360 nm) are observed only for the highest Cu-loaded samples (600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15), indicating the formation of bulk-like CuO species at elevated Cu loadings. However, the gradual increase in absorption in region III (600–900 nm) for all Cu-containing materials (Fig. S11, Supplementary) suggests the formation of various amounts of bulk-like CuO.

The estimated optical bandgap energies (*E_g*) derived from Tauc plots (Fig. 6C) show a decreasing trend with increasing Cu content and calcination temperature. This bandgap narrowing reflects the evolution from isolated Cu²⁺ species to more aggregated and crystalline CuO domains, in agreement with literature observations [56,57].

Fig. 3. STEM-EDS analysis and HRTEM images of 800-IMP-Cu5.

Fig. 4. STEM-EDS analysis and HRTEM images of 800-IMP-Cu15.

3.1.4. Surface properties of mixed metal oxides

XPS studies confirm that the surface of the materials is dominated by

the presence of Mg, Al, Cu, O and C (Fig. 7, Figs. S12 and 13). The contents of individual elements (excluding C, its concentration

Fig. 5. STEM-EDS analysis and HRTEM images of 600-IMP-Cu15.

Fig. 6. H₂-TPR profiles of samples (A) 600-IMP-Cu series and (B) 800-IMP-Cu series (C) UV-vis-DRS absorption bands.

completes the surface composition to 100 %) are shown in Table 3. In the XPS Mg 2p (Fig. S12, Supplementary) and Al 2p spectra (Fig. S13, Supplementary), the presence of single components corresponding to Mg²⁺ (49.9 ± 0.3 eV) and Al³⁺ (74.1 ± 0.3 eV), respectively, is found. In the case of the latter analyzed region for the Cu-containing samples, an

additional component appears at higher binding energies, originating from the emission of photoelectrons from the Cu 3p level [58]. More information about the chemical environment of these components is provided by the analysis of the XPS O 1s region (Fig. 7 B and C). In these spectra, three components are observed at 530.1 ± 0.3 eV, 531.4 ± 0.1

Fig. 7. High-resolution XPS spectra of (A) Cu 2p for all Cu-containing samples (B) O 1s for 600-IMP series and (C) O 1s for 800-IMP series.

Table 3

Surface composition determined by XPS.

Sample code	Magnesium	Aluminum	Copper		Oxygen		
	Mg ²⁺	Al ³⁺	Cu ²⁺ -O ²⁻	Cu ²⁺ -OH/CO ₃ ²⁻	O ²⁻	OH ⁻	CO ₃ ²⁻
	49.9 ± 0.3 eV (Mg 2p)	74.1 ± 0.3 eV (Al 2p)	933.1 ± 0.2 eV (Cu 2p _{3/2})	935.0 ± 0.1 eV (Cu 2p _{3/2})	530.1 ± 0.3 eV (O 1 s)	531.4 ± 0.1 eV (O 1 s)	532.8 ± 0.2 eV (O 1 s)
600-MgAl	23.1	10.2	–	–	3.4	47.1	3.3
600-IMP-Cu5	22.9	10.0	0.2	0.2	3.1	47.2	4.4
600-IMP-Cu10	23.2	10.2	0.4	0.5	6.0	46.5	3.0
600-IMP-Cu15	22.5	10.1	0.7	0.7	5.5	45.5	4.3
800-MgAl	26.0	10.7	–	–	8.4	41.9	4.2
800-IMP-Cu5	25.3	10.5	0.3	0.4	13.2	32.4	5.6
800-IMP-Cu10	26.3	11.9	0.8	0.7	16.2	27.6	4.4
800-IMP-Cu15	26.9	12.5	1.2	1.1	18.5	23.9	4.9

eV and 532.8 ± 0.2 eV, attributed to lattice O²⁻, OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻ species, respectively [21]. The participation of lattice oxygen increases significantly with increasing the calcination temperature from 600 °C to 800 °C and additionally introducing larger amounts of Cu. Nevertheless, in all cases, hydroxyl groups play a dominant role on the surface. They are most numerous for all samples of 600-IMP series and the 800-IMP materials with lower Cu content. The surface of all studied catalysts is also covered with a certain amount of carbonate groups. It must be noted that the OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻ species identified on the catalyst surface in the Cu 2p spectra, and clearly confirmed by the O 1s spectra, do not originate from incompletely decomposed precursors remaining after calcination. Instead, they result from the adsorption of moisture and atmospheric CO₂ during storage of the samples after synthesis. Their presence should not be surprising due to the contact of calcined preparations with atmospheric air containing CO₂ and the significant basicity of Mg-Al-O surface. The hydroxyl and carbonate groups are also formed with the involvement of Cu²⁺, as evidenced by the presence of two components in

the XPS Cu 2p_{3/2} region (Fig. 7A). The first peak at 933.1 ± 0.2 eV is typical for Cu²⁺ bound to lattice oxygen, while the second one at 935.0 ± 0.1 eV is a result of OH⁻ and CO₃²⁻ bonds with surface Cu²⁺ ions [59]. In all the tested catalysts, the share of Cu²⁺ species bonded to O²⁻ and OH⁻/CO₃²⁻ is comparable. However, it is worth noting the total Cu content on the surface increases with the total Cu loading, and is also noticeably higher for the 800-IMP series.

Although the component at 531.4 eV in the O 1s spectra is mainly attributed to surface hydroxyl groups, it cannot be excluded that this signal also partially originates from chemisorbed oxygen species associated with oxygen-deficient sites. Such an interpretation, often found in the literature, links this component to the presence of oxygen vacancies. However, this assignment should be considered with caution, as the corresponding O 1s emission arises from oxygen atoms that occupy or compensate these vacancies after exposure to air, and from hydroxyl groups that can naturally form on the material surface, not only from those associated with oxygen-deficient sites. The extent of this surface

hydroxylation strongly depends on the chemical and phase composition of the oxide surface. In Mg–Al–O-based systems, hydroxyl groups form readily even in the absence of significant structural defects. Consequently, the higher relative intensity of this peak for samples calcined at 600 °C may primarily reflect a greater surface reactivity and a higher ability to form or stabilize such adsorbed oxygen species, while also suggesting that these samples may possess a higher number of oxygen vacancies compared to the 800 °C series.

The results of *reactive frontal chromatography*, summarized in Table 4, disclose that a copper surface area (S_{Cu}) expressed per g of a sample and g of copper is influenced by a copper loading. An increase of Cu content leads to a decrease in S_{Cu} ($m_{Cu}^2/g_{(Cu)}$), which can be attributed to the formation of more bulky or aggregated CuO species. These findings align with the observations from TEM, H₂-TPR and UV–vis-DRS analyses. At the same time, the S_{Cu} , expressed per g of the sample, increases with the higher copper loading, which is expected due to the higher number of Cu introduced into the samples.

A comparison of the samples with the same copper loadings does not reveal significant differences in the S_{Cu} ($m_{Cu}^2/g_{(Cu)}$), regardless the calcination temperature. The obtained results suggest that the wet-impregnation method followed by re-calcination at 600 °C and 800 °C does not significantly affect copper exposure, when comparing samples of the same copper loading. However, when copper surface area is recalculated to the total surface area of the samples, it becomes evident that a decrease in S_{BET} corresponds to an increase in copper exposure.

The *temperature programmed desorption of ammonia* (NH₃-TPD) profiles, presented in Fig. 8, show two main peaks corresponding to the low-temperature desorption (160–180 °C) and high-temperature desorption of NH₃ (275–320 °C). The first desorption peak is associated with NH₃ bound to weak-strength acid sites, while the second peak is attributed to the medium-strong acid sites [60]. While it is not possible to distinguish between Lewis and Brønsted acid sites using these profiles, it is well-established that mixed metal oxides derived from the calcination of hydrotalcites exhibit both types of sites. The Lewis acid sites are typically associated with Al–O–Mg species, while Brønsted acid sites are related to surface protons [39,61]. The calculated peak areas (Fig. 8) show that the 600-IMP samples exhibit a higher total amount of acid sites compared to the 800-IMP samples.

3.2. Catalytic efficiency evaluation

The reference samples, 600-MgAl and 800-MgAl, are found to be inactive as catalysts of ammonia oxidation, showing NH₃ conversion below 5 % within the studied temperature range (Fig. 9A). This confirms that copper play a crucial role in the catalytic performance. Among the copper containing catalysts, the 600-IMP-Cu5 and 800-IMP-Cu5 samples demonstrate limited activity, achieving less than 20 % NH₃ conversion, which makes them unsuitable for efficient NH₃-SCO catalysis.

Samples IMP-600: Samples with higher copper loadings, 10 and 15 wt %, show improved catalytic performance in comparison to 600-IMP-Cu5. The 600-IMP-Cu10 and 600-IMP-Cu15 samples achieve maximum NH₃ conversion of 54 % and 83 %, respectively, at 350 °C, with corresponding N₂ selectivity 81 % and 70 % (Fig. 9A). The catalytic efficiency of these materials increases progressively with temperature,

Table 4
Results of reactive frontal chromatography.

Sample	Cu surface area (S_{Cu})		
	$m_{Cu}^2/g_{(sample)}$	$m_{Cu}^2/g_{(Cu)}$	$m_{Cu}^2/m_{(sample)}^2$
600-IMP-Cu5	3.3	70	0.017
600-IMP-Cu10	5.6	57	0.036
600-IMP-Cu15	6.6	46	0.046
800-IMP-Cu5	3.5	68	0.031
800-IMP-Cu10	5.4	48	0.062
800-IMP-Cu15	6.7	43	0.112

Fig. 8. Results of the NH₃-TPD measurements.

while selectivity is decreasing. The 600-IMP-Cu10 sample shows an NH₃ conversion improvement from 27 % at 325 °C to 54 % at 350 °C, accompanied by the increase in N₂ yield from 22 % to 44 %. Side products, predominantly NO, remain minimal at these temperatures, with yields of 5 % and 7 % at 325 and 350 °C, respectively. However, increasing the copper loading to 15 wt % (600-IMP-Cu15) leads to higher side product formation, with NO being the dominant by-products species (8 % and 20 % at 325 and 350 °C, respectively). This suggests that higher copper loadings promote secondary reactions, increasing NO formation.

Samples series 800-IMP: The 800-IMP-Cu10 and 800-IMP-Cu15 samples show comparable catalytic efficiency at 350 °C as 600-IMP-Cu10 and 600-IMP-Cu15 samples, achieving NH₃ conversions at 56 % and 87 %, respectively, with N₂ selectivity of 70 % and 61 % (Fig. 9A). Similar to the 600-IMP series, the efficiency of the 800-IMP samples improves with temperature. At 350 °C, NH₃ conversion over 800-IMP-Cu10 increases from 23 % at 325 °C to 55 %, while N₂ yield rises from 15 % to 39 %. Side-products yield remains low at 325 °C (approx. 8 %) but increases to 16 % at 350 °C, where NO dominates (Fig. 9B). This indicates that higher copper loadings in the 800-IMP series also promote the undesirable side reactions at elevated temperatures.

The *catalytic efficiency evaluation* highlights the significant influence of copper loading on catalytic performance. The materials calcined at 600 °C exhibit similar catalytic properties compared to the 800-IMP

Fig. 9. Results of catalytic tests (A) Conversion and selectivity (B) Products yield and unreacted NH₃. Experimental conditions: catalysts mass = 200 mg, [NH₃] = 0.035 mol. %, [O₂] = 20 mol. %, [N₂] = 79.65 mol. %, total flow rate = 100 ml/min, WHSV = 500 ml/(min.g).

series, whereby side product yield tends to increase with copper content (Fig. 9B). The only difference observed for both series is related to slightly different N₂ yield – slightly more by-products were formed for samples calcined at 800 °C.

3.2.1. Stability tests

The stability of catalytic performance was assessed using the 600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15 samples at a reaction temperature of 350 °C (Fig. 10). Both catalysts demonstrate consistent catalytic efficiency over the 70-hour testing period, with no significant fluctuations observed in ammonia conversion or N₂ selectivity.

The results of stability tests show that both catalysts, regardless of calcination temperature, are well-suited for long-term NH₃-SCO

applications. The absence of any significant decline in catalytic efficiency or selectivity, highlights the durability of these materials under reaction conditions.

4. Discussion

This study investigated the catalytic behavior of hydrotalcite-derived Mg-Al mixed oxides impregnated with varying copper contents (5–15 wt %) and calcined at two different temperatures (600 °C and 800 °C), focusing on their catalytic efficiency in selective catalytic oxidation of ammonia (NH₃-SCO). The results provide insight into the interplay between Cu loading, dispersion, which is directly affected by the phase composition, redox and acid properties, and catalytic performance, and

Fig. 10. Stability tests over (A) 600-IMP-Cu15 and (B) 800-IMP-Cu15. Experimental conditions: temperature 350 °C, catalysts mass = 200 mg, [NH₃] = 0.035 mol. %, [O₂] = 20 mol. %, [N₂] = 79.65 mol. %, total flow rate = 100 ml/min, WHSV = 500 ml/(min.g).

demonstrate how these features are influenced by the synthesis route and thermal treatment.

The relationships between the catalytic efficiency observed over the samples from series 600-IMP and 800-IMP vs BET specific surface area, H₂ consumption up to 400 °C and Cu surface area is presented in Fig. 11.

4.0.1. Copper loading and catalytic activity

The reference materials (600-MgAl and 800-MgAl) showed no significant NH₃ conversion, confirming that the presence of copper is essential for catalytic activity in NH₃-SCO. Among Cu-containing samples, those with low Cu content (5 wt%) are characterized by poor activity, reaching NH₃ conversion below 20 % and limited N₂ yields, irrespective of calcination temperature. In contrast, the catalysts with 10 and 15 wt% Cu showed enhanced efficiency, reaching up to 87 % NH₃ conversion and 70–81 % N₂ selectivity at 350 °C.

However, increasing Cu loading beyond 10 wt% also led to increased formation of undesired side-products. In 600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15, the NO yield reached up to 20 % at 350 °C, compared to 5–7 % in the Cu10 catalysts. This indicates that while high Cu loadings improve conversion, they can also favor over-oxidation pathways, reducing N₂ selectivity. These observations confirm the need for a balanced Cu distribution.

Both, 600-IMP and 800-IMP series showed comparable trends, suggesting that the total Cu content is a more dominant factor in determining catalytic activity than the calcination temperature. However, differences in copper dispersion and phase composition indicate that calcination affects the structural evolution of the catalyst and influences side-product formation.

4.0.2. Influence of surface area on materials efficiency

The BET surface area (S_{BET}) revealed similar trends valid for both series 600-IMP and 800-IMP: the evaluated S_{BET} significantly decreased with the increase of copper loading and calcination temperature. For instance, the 600-IMP samples show higher surface area in comparison to the corresponding 800-IMP materials, while the reference samples exhibit the highest S_{BET} (Table 2). Simultaneously, it is worth noting that the samples with the lowest surface area (600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15) shows the best catalytic performance.

The decrease in surface area across both series is likely due to increased crystallinity (crystallite size) in the samples. Our previous work [40] shows, that lower calcination temperature (up to 500–600 °C) favors the formation of low-crystallinity simple oxide forms, whereas higher temperatures facilitate the development of well-crystallized, more complex mixed metal oxides. This temperature-dependent influence on surface area is further supported by the calculated crystallite sizes (Table 2).

Moreover, the wet-impregnation process required a subsequent re-calcination step after copper addition. This additional exposure to high temperatures likely contributed not only to the formation of desired CuO phases but also to the growth of previously formed periclase and spinel like-crystallites.

The specific surface area is often considered as a critical factor in heterogeneous catalysis since highly developed surface area promotes the exposure of active centers and lower the possibility of pores blockage. However, our results suggest otherwise. For materials presented in this work, similar catalytic efficiency is observed when comparing samples with the same Cu loading. Therefore, specific surface area does not appear to have significant impact on the materials efficiency (Fig. 11A).

Fig. 11. NH₃ conversion and yield of N₂ vs. (A) BET specific surface area, (B) hydrogen consumption up to 400 °C (C) copper surface area per g of sample (D) copper surface area.

4.0.3. Influence of copper reducibility and accessibility

To explore what factors might impact the catalytic efficiency, we examined the form and accessibility of copper on the surface. A detailed analysis of samples morphology (Fig. 12) reveals the presence of plate-like structures resembling hydrangea flowers. These structures are similar to the CuO nanostructures reported by Gao and Liu [62]. According to their findings, CuO structures originating from $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, during the hydrothermal reactions form platelet-like crystals. The final shape and the level of aggregation is related to the concentration of precursor: the higher concentration favors the formation of bigger and well-developed plate-like structures [62]. The SEM micrographs of 600-IMP and 800-IMP (Fig. 2D and related Fig. S1-S8) confirm the formation of plate-like structures with the increase of both copper loading and calcination temperature. Since copper was introduced via the wet-impregnation method, the distribution of Cu particles is expected to be limited to the sample surface. This assumption is fully confirmed by the XPS spectra, which showed the enrichment of the external surface of the studied materials in Cu with the increase of its loading and calcination temperature (Fig. 7 and Table 3). It is worth noting that under the conditions of a sample storage prior to catalytic tests, various Cu-containing surface species are formed. Hydroxyl and carbonate groups play a dominant role in the external surface composition in addition to the expected oxide forms. Nevertheless, in a reaction environment at elevated temperature they can be relatively easily transformed into more catalytically active sites.

The comparison of catalytic efficiency and hydrogen consumption up to 400 °C (Fig. 11B) reveals a clear correlation between samples reducibility and catalytic behavior. Both, 600-IMP-Cu5 and 800-IMP-Cu5 exhibit the lowest ammonia conversion and the lowest N_2 yield. Their H_2 consumption up to 400 °C is the lowest in comparison to other samples in both series. The increase in hydrogen consumption correlates directly with the increase in copper content.

The findings of current work contrast with our previous research (Górecka et al. [21]), where we observed the best catalytic efficiency for samples with the lowest Cu loading (5 mol. % ~ cca. 6.25 wt%). It allows us to assume that not only the Cu loading, but also the incorporation method influences the catalytic efficiency. The previously studied samples were obtained by co-precipitation method, where Cu was incorporated during the synthesis step. It results in formation of CuO dispersed and bulk-like species with surface area lower than that of samples from current work prepared by impregnation method. The presence of bulk-like forms increased with the Cu loading as the results of overall specific surface area drop and enhanced crystallites growth [21]. We observed that the catalytic activity highly depended on the amount of CuO bulk-like forms: for materials with higher Cu loading the NH_3 conversion was close to 100 %, while the N_2 selectivity was poor, showing higher formation of side products, especially NO. Similar effects were observed for materials of different chemical composition of the parent material matrix: CuMgAl, CuFeAl, CuZnAl ($M^{2+}/M^{3+} = 2.03$) [9,21,22,40]: the process selectivity drops with increasing loading of Cu.

In contrast, the materials in this study were prepared by Cu-

impregnation of calcined Mg-Al hydrotalcites. This modification appears to significantly influence both the physicochemical and catalytic properties of the resulting materials, showing that both – ammonia conversion and N_2 selectivity increase with copper wt. % loading. Observations were attributed to the presence of dispersed Cu species linked to high selectivity rather than bulk-like copper oxide responsible for effective however unselective oxidation process. In case of 600-IMP-Cu5 and 800-IMP-Cu5, the reduction profiles showed occurrence of hardly reducible Cu forms, that were not observed for samples prepared by coprecipitation and this hardly reducible forms were ascribed to the isolated copper species and Cu species influenced by interaction with spinel (Fig. 6) that we consider to be inactive in NH_3 -SCO process.

Analysis of copper surface area (Fig. 11C) reveals a clear relationship: catalytic performance depends on copper exposure on the surface. When comparing the $S_{\text{Cu/sample}}$, it is evident that counterpart materials exhibit similar S_{Cu} values, as well as comparable NH_3 conversion levels, however with slightly different N_2 yield – more by-products were formed for samples calcined at 800 °C. XPS method shows that the surface of 800-IMP samples is enriched by Cu in comparison to 600-IMP (Table 3). Obtained results are related to the differences in specific surface area of 600-MgAl and 800-MgAl supports as well as active phase crystallinity. Since the Cu-forms are expected to be deposited only on the surface support, the impregnation method leads to formation of thicker layer of Cu-precursor on the 800-IMP samples in comparison to 600-IMP, because of the higher initial S_{BET} of 600-MgAl support and more severe calcination conditions can cause higher level of active phase surface aggregation. The analysis of the RFC and XPS results shows that the materials calcined at lower temperature still have potential for surface incorporation of increased copper loading while preserving desired dispersion level.

4.0.4. Influence of acidity

NH_3 -TPD results show that the calcination temperature also significantly influences the surface acidity of the catalysts. Increasing the calcination temperature promotes the formation of more stable spinel-like oxide phases and decreases the amount of surface hydroxyl groups and weak acid sites, while moderate temperatures favor the presence of highly dispersed CuO and possibly also higher concentration of oxygen vacancies as observed from XPS. The high dispersion of CuO species is expected to closely relate to both the surface acidity as well as concentration of oxygen vacancies since dispersed CuO particles generate a larger number of Cu–O–Mg(Al) interfacial sites that can act as Lewis acid sites and simultaneously promote can the formation of surface defects [63,64]. In contrast, the sintering of copper species and the development of stable Cu–Mg–Al spinel phases at higher temperatures reduce both the number of accessible acid sites and the reactive surface structure, thereby weakening the redox–acid synergy. Acid sites primarily govern NH_3 adsorption and activation; therefore, the abundance and strength of these sites affect the surface coverage and reactivity of nitrogen-containing intermediates. On the other hand, oxygen vacancies facilitate O_2 activation and the oxidation of intermediate species [65]. In

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs (SE+BSE mode) of plate-like structures observed for 800-IMP-Cu15.

this context, copper species play a key redox role. Highly dispersed CuO and $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^+$ redox pairs provide active centers for O_2 activation and the stepwise oxidation of adsorbed NH_3 or NH_x intermediates toward N_2 , acting through a Mars–van Krevelen-type mechanism. In contrast, copper incorporated into bulk or spinel-like Cu–Mg–Al oxide phases exhibits lower redox accessibility and contributes less to the redox cycle, which limits controlled oxygen activation and may favor the formation of NO_x .

Our findings, so far, underline the role of copper accessibility, reducibility, dispersion as well as catalyst acidity. Thus, choose of support of well-developed surface area and presence of desired Cu dispersed but not isolated species should result in overall improvement of catalytic efficiency.

These conclusions are consistent with previous studies, where catalysts featuring highly accessible and finely dispersed copper species were found to exhibit superior NH_3 -SCO performance and enhanced N_2 selectivity. Gang et al. [66] studied the supported $\text{CuO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts obtained by incipient wetness impregnation. Among prepared samples containing 5, 10 and 15 wt% Cu, the catalyst with 10 wt% Cu exhibited the best performance in NH_3 -SCO, reaching $\approx 90\%$ NH_3 conversion with 97% selectivity to N_2 at 300 °C (experimental conditions: $\text{NH}_3 = 1.14\text{ V}\%$; $\text{O}_2 = 8.21\text{ V}\%$; total flow rate: 74.7 ml/min; catalysts mass = 0.2 g). This superior behavior was attributed to the predominance of highly dispersed CuAl_2O_4 -like surface species, whereas an increased Cu loading (15 wt%) led to the formation of bulk-like CuO, which was less active and less selective comparing to CuAl_2O_4 [66]. A subsequent and expanded investigation was carried out by Liang et al. [52]. $\text{Cu}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts were prepared via impregnation with different copper precursors (nitrate, sulfate, and acetate salts), each containing 10 wt% Cu. Crystalline CuO aggregates were detected in samples calcined between 673 and 1073 K, whereas higher temperatures promoted a formation of a spinel CuAl_2O_4 phase. The catalyst prepared using the acetate precursor achieved 95% NH_3 conversion and 97.5% selectivity towards N_2 ($\text{NH}_3 = 1000\text{ ppm}$; $\text{O}_2 = 10\text{ vol}\%$; total flow rate = 100 ml/min; catalyst mass = 0.2 g; WHSV = 500 ml/(min•g)). Interestingly, in contrast to the results of Gang et al. [66], Liang et al. [52] suggested that dispersed CuO species were catalytically more active and selective for N_2 formation in NH_3 -SCO than the CuAl_2O_4 phase. A similar trend, where finely dispersed CuO species promote higher NH_3 conversion and N_2 selectivity, has also been observed in studies by Hung [17,67], who studied CuO– CeO_2 mixed oxides with varying CuO: CeO_2 molar ratios. However, these co-precipitated samples exhibited relatively low surface area (below 90 m^2/g), which limited the rate of ammonia conversion. This drawback was addressed by Wang et al. [68], who synthesized CuO– CeO_2 catalysts by a surfactant-directed method, yielding materials with a BET surface area above 130 m^2/g and highly dispersed CuO species strongly interacting with nanocrystalline CeO_2 . The sample containing 10 wt% Cu calcined at 500 °C reached complete NH_3 conversion with N_2 selectivity above 95% already at 250 °C ($\text{NH}_3 = 1000\text{ ppm}$; $\text{O}_2 = 10\text{ vol}\%$; total flow rate = 100 ml/min; GHSV = 40 000 h^{-1}), outperforming the co-precipitated counterparts. The enhanced activity and selectivity were attributed to the high dispersion of CuO and the strong Cu–O–Ce interfacial interaction. Overall, these studies [13,17,52,66–68] clearly demonstrate that finely dispersed CuO species are essential for achieving high catalytic efficiency and N_2 selectivity in NH_3 -SCO.

However, the long-term catalytic stability of the previously discussed catalysts was not verified in those studies. A comprehensive stability assessment of catalysts containing active CuO sites was later reported by Ran et al. [69]. Their work focused on CuO/TiO_2 catalysts in which well-dispersed CuO_x species were supported on the anatase TiO_2 . Under reaction conditions ($\text{NH}_3 = 500\text{ ppm}$; $\text{O}_2 = 5\text{ vol}\%$; Ar balance; total flow rate = 200 ml/min; GHSV = 60 000 h^{-1}), catalytic activity increased with both temperature and CuO loading. The 1.5 wt% and 2 wt% CuO/TiO_2 catalysts achieved nearly 100% NH_3 conversion at 300 °C, with N_2 selectivity around 89%. Nevertheless, N_2 selectivity rapidly decreased when the temperature was raised to 350 °C, indicating the onset of non-

selective oxidation pathways. A long-term stability test performed for the 1.5 wt% CuO/TiO_2 catalyst at 300 °C ($\text{NH}_3 = 500\text{ ppm}$; $\text{O}_2 = 5\text{ vol}\%$; total flow rate = 100 ml/min; GHSV = 40 000 h^{-1}) demonstrated excellent durability, maintaining nearly 100% NH_3 conversion and $\approx 90\%$ N_2 selectivity over 80 h. In contrast, in the long-term stability tests conducted in the present study, the 600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15 catalysts maintained comparable or even superior stability and selectivity at a significantly higher reaction temperature of 350 °C. Specifically, NH_3 conversions of $\approx 60\%$ and 80% were achieved for the 600-IMP-Cu15 and 800-IMP-Cu15 catalysts, respectively, while N_2 selectivity remained around 80% for both. These results indicate that our impregnated catalysts exhibit robust high-temperature stability, preserving N_2 selectivity at conditions where CuO/TiO_2 systems from Ran et al. already suffered a notable decline in selectivity.

In the development of NH_3 -SCO catalysts, it is important to recognize that, in addition to intrinsic activity and selectivity, catalyst performance can be significantly influenced by components commonly present in real exhaust gas streams, such as water vapor and sulfur-containing species. Water is known to compete with NH_3 for adsorption sites, while SO_2 may cause reversible or irreversible deactivation of active centers. For this reason, the evaluation of catalyst behavior in the presence of H_2O and SO_x represents a relevant and necessary aspect of NH_3 -SCO research. Accordingly, the investigation under dry reaction conditions and the resulting structure–performance relationships related to copper dispersion, surface accessibility, and redox properties presented in this study constitute a crucial foundation for future investigations under conditions closer to industrial exhaust gas compositions.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the catalytic performance of Cu-containing mixed metal oxides is significantly influenced by the copper loading, its accessibility and form of Cu-species. For impregnation method, the high copper loadings enhance NH_3 conversion and N_2 selectivity due to formation of mostly dispersed species, with the samples of 15 wt% loading of Cu showing the best overall performance. Since still some bulk CuO species were formed, further refinements are needed to suppress side-product formation and improve selectivity. The stability of these materials under prolonged testing indicates their potential for industrial applications, though future work should address challenges such as water vapor resistance and long-term stability in real-world conditions.

The findings offer valuable insights for the design of advanced catalysts for NH_3 -SCO:

- The presence of dispersed, non-isolated CuO species, is crucial for the materials activity and selectivity to N_2 . Formation of bulk-like species leads to generation of side products; thus, the materials development methods should focus on improvement of CuO dispersion.
- The use of support of well-developed surface area should allow increase of copper loading without the formation of bulk-like species and drop of catalytic efficiency.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used an artificial intelligence-based language editing tool to improve the clarity and style of the text. After using this tool, the authors thoroughly reviewed and edited the content and take full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sylwia Górecka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original

draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Katerina Kupkova**: Visualization, Investigation. **Katerina Pacultova**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Tereza Bílková**: Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Kamil Górecki**: Visualization, Investigation. **Anna Rokicińska**: Visualization, Investigation. **Piotr Kuśtrowski**: Writing – review & editing. **Grzegorz Słowik**: Investigation, Data curation. **Lucie Obalová**: Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Funding

The work was supported by the OP JAK project “INOVO!!!”, No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008588 supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports and co-financed by the European Union. Experimental results were accomplished by using Large Research Infrastructure ENREGAT supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under project No. LM2023056. The XPS study was carried out using research infrastructure funded by the European Union in the framework of the Smart Growth Operational Programme, Measure 4.2; Grant No. POIR.04.02.00-00-D001/20, “ATOMIN 2.0 – Center for materials research on ATOMIC scale for the INnovative economy”. The financial support of the Strategic Programme Excellence Initiative at Jagiellonian University, used for servicing measurement systems, is also appreciated.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to Alexandr Martaus for XRD analyses, Lenka Matějová and Zuzana Jankovská for nitrogen physisorption measurements.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2026.165973>.

Data availability

Data are available in repository Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/16872589>.

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